

EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN PARENTING STYLE
AND ADOLESCENT ANTISOCIAL BEHAVIOUR IN
IFAKO-IJAIYE LOCAL GOVERNMENT,
LAGOS STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour among adolescents from four selected secondary school in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government Area, Lagos State. The study utilized a descriptive survey design. The sample size consisted of 252 students randomly selected from four selected secondary school in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government. The instrument used to elicit information from the respondents was structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The reliability of the instrument using Cronbach alpha of $r=0.843$. Descriptive analysis was used to collect the data and was further subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to test for the association between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour. The result shows that there was a significant relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour ($r = 0.971^{**}$, $N=252$, $p=0.000<.05$) among adolescents. This study concluded with the finding that antisocial behavior is a part of everyday life, and affects millions of people around the world.

Therefore, antisocial behavior needs to be carefully examined. It is important to understand not only what antisocial behavior is, but also to have a better understanding of how it is created. Positive parenting may possibly lead to a decrease in antisocial behavior. It is therefore recommended that family focused programs should be organized for parents to help develop and maintain effective monitoring and discipline strategies, parents should supervise children and serve as role model, Stakeholders should handle cases of antisocial behaviour individually and other factors like childhood experiences, hereditary, environment etc should be considered to rehabilitate such offenders in rare cases if the parent of the offender practices authoritative parenting styles.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Adolescence comes from the Latin word 'Adolescere' which means to grow up or grow into maturity. The World Health Organization (WHO) places the age range from 10 to 19 years. It is the period of transition between childhood and adulthood; puberty to adulthood. This is a phase of life when adolescents experience remarkable physiological changes, which include the development of secondary sex characteristics, growth spurts, and hormonal changes. At that stage, adolescents possess increased communication skills, enjoy academic activities, high level of curiosity, and sometimes live in a world of their own even in the midst of others. They become more argumentative in wanting to prove their point as right (Onoyase & Ebenuwa, 2018).

Furthermore, at this stage, they move from homosexual relationships to heterosexual attraction; they are expected to know what the family and society expect from them, the type of personality and self-concept which can lead to a healthy personality or, in contrast, role confusion. According to (Okafor & Nnoli, 2010) adolescents are known to become more independent of their parents' will earlier than before (Mburza, 2006). They create a separate world for themselves using language and expressions only known to their clique. Peer influence plays a significant role in the lives of adolescents; peer influence tends to overrule their parents, and this often leads to serious disagreements with their parents or guardians (Onoyase & Ebenuwa, 2018).

Parents are parents, whether they are married or not, or the child is adopted or biological; any person who, although not a natural parent, has parental responsibility. It is defined as a person who has a legal parent and child relationship with a child, which imposes on the person legal rights, privileges, duties, and obligations. Parenting can be fulfilling, heartbreaking, time-consuming, and difficult. Parent-child relationships are an important aspect of a child's life.

Parental influence cannot be overemphasized when addressing children's antisocial and prosocial behavior is being addressed because their actions, reactions, and discipline styles basically mold and shape them into adults. Diana Baumrind's concepts of parenting can be explained by two independent factors: control (demandingness) and warmth (responsiveness). Parental demandingness depicts the parents' level of control, expectations, and demands, while parental responsiveness is the emotional aspect of parenting, which includes the level of parental nurturance, emotional expression, and positive reinforcement of a child's opinion. The combination of these two factors in varying degrees creates the

behaviour and attitude that can be classified into the three parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive (Esmeralda, 2015).

Authoritative parenting is high in demandingness and responsiveness; it conveys the reasoning behind rules and use power and shaping to reinforce objectives. Authoritarian parents are highly demanding and low in warmth. responsiveness, often strict, is termed "cold" and unemotional. They emphasize absolute obedience without explanation and exhibit a low level of trust for their children. exercise power, verbal hostility, and discourage open communication (Donnah, 2014), children trained by such parents may develop low self-esteem and are at risk of becoming deviant once they are free of their parents' clutch. The third style, permissive parenting, is low in demandingness and high in responsiveness. permissive parents do not impose any rules on their children; their children can do what they want and when they want. Permissive parents can either be supportive (indulgent) or not caring about their children (neglectful), they behave in a punitive manner and acceptable way towards child impulse, desire, and action; they avoid the use of control and do not encourage them to obey externally defined standards (Esmeralda, 2015).

Antisocial behavior is a broad construct that describes not only delinquency or crime but also disruptive behavior that is contrary to the accepted social and moral norms in society. This includes juvenile delinquency, vandalism, sexual promiscuity, stealing, excessive smoking, rudeness, use of illegal drugs, underage drinking, gambling, fighting, bullying, verbal abuse, etc. (Onoyase & Ebebuwa, 2018). The quality of a person as an adult is determined by their quality of life as a child; therefore, signs of antisocial behaviour should not be overlooked with a view to recognizing their onset in children and taking corrective actions to rectify them before they get out of hand (Nwanneka, 2015) . Several studies have related the age at which an individual delinquent behaviour begins to the (2016) number of offenses committed in the subsequent years and found that the average number of (2017) offenses tends to decline as their age of onset increases (Clemens, 2006).

Parents serve as models for their children to imitate; a parent who uses physical aggression in punishing their child is serving as an aggressive model, as it has been proven that the severity of parental punishment for aggression is associated with the child's own display of aggression.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Antisocial behaviour in Nigeria has clouded the acceptable norms of society. All manner of degrading behaviour has filled the news line every day, from grievous offenses like murder, fraud and corruption, robbery, terrorism, vandalism, and rape to deviant acts like incest and hate speech. This behaviour has gained a foothold in the lives of adolescents and adults. This study sought to examine one of the main factors that could contribute to such behaviour in adolescents in Ifako- Ijaiye Local Government, Lagos State.

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is significant in examining parenting styles that could predict future antisocial behaviour among adolescents in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government, Lagos State. It hopes to understand the correlation between parent-child relationships and antisocial behaviour in adolescents.

These findings would enable stakeholders - Government, religious leaders, community leaders, teachers, and parents know how parenting styles can contribute to antisocial behaviour in adolescents, the role of poor parenting styles in the formation of antisocial behaviour in children, and what structure to put in place once a child is observed to exhibit antisocial behaviour.

1.4 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour; determining adolescents' perceptions antisocial behaviour.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To determine the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.
- To identify the predominant parenting styles among the adolescents.
- To identify the kinds of antisocial behaviour common in the area of study.
- To assess adolescent perception towards antisocial behaviour.
- To examine the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour.

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- ·What is the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents?
- ·What is the predominant parenting style among the adolescents?
- What are the kinds of antisocial behaviour common in the area of study?
- ·What is the adolescent perception towards antisocial behaviour?
- ·What is the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour?

1.7 HYPOTHESIS

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour among adolescents.

1.8 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERMS

ADOLESCENCE: Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood; it lasts for a decade. It is marked by the onset of puberty. Early adolescence starts from ages 11 to 13, middle adolescence from ages 14 to 18 years, and late adolescence starts from ages 18 to 24 years.

PARENTING STYLES: Parenting styles are psychological constructs representing standard strategies that parents use in the upbringing of a child, it is a representation of how parents respond to and demand from their children.

FAMILY: Family is a socially sanctioned group that extends the rights and obligations of marriage to parenthood, uniting the marital partners with one or more children who belong to them by virtue of blood or adoption.

ANTISOCIAL BEHAVIOUR: Anti-social behaviour is defined as behaviour by a person that causes or is likely to cause harm, harassment, alarm, or distress to a person not of the same household as the individual. (Antisocial Behaviour Act 2003 and Police Reform and Social Responsibility Act 2011).

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Adolescence may be viewed as a transitional stage in human development from childhood to adulthood during which an individual goes through many changes, such formation of new values, attitudes, and behaviors that are socially acceptable for adults forms (Nimfa, 2014)

According to developmental specialists in the USA, early adolescence starts at ages 11 to 13, middle adolescence from ages 14 to 18 and late adolescence from ages 18 to 24 years. Changes that influence adolescents' development can be grouped into psychosocial and psychobiological changes. Psycho-biological changes are universal, while psychosocial changes are culture-specific (Ausubel, 1954). There is a greater likelihood of biological, psychological, and social changes that prepare adolescents for adulthood (McLaughlin, 2015), hence, the importance of the study of their perception of their primary group, which includes their parents and friends, because these are the people they interact with the most and are likely to be influenced by (Brad, 2015). The early adolescents compare themselves more with their contemporaries regarding their own abilities (Helfert & Warschburger, 2013). If they sense that they are not performing according to the standards of others, it might negatively affect their psychological health and self-esteem (McLaughlin & King, 2015).

However, for this study, emphasis will be placed on the placed on the parents as an independent variable and how parenting styles can lead to low self-esteem and the possibility of antisocial behaviour in adolescents, as they spend more time with their families, which in turn can lead to either positive or negative outcomes depending on how adolescents perceive, see, and evaluate others (Brendgen et al., 2013).

According to Hall (1904), human development occurs in the following stages: infancy (birth to age 4), childhood (4 to 8 years), youth (8 to 12 years), and adolescence (12 to mid-20's). Moreover, he viewed adolescence as a period of storm and stress that is turbulent and transitional.

Adolescence seems to represent a scene of smoothly evolving changes in development and is not necessarily any more or less stressful than other developmental stages, as implied by social constructs (Nimfa, 2014).

Intellectual competency views of adolescents.

One of the qualitative changes that occur in adolescents' years is that they begin to understand the thought processes of others and interact with the environment in a new and different way. They develop a close group of friends, which helps them with their own individuality, and they share new views of moral thinking together. They also develop abstract thinking abilities, which allows them to view their social environment, learn to cope with abstract thinking, and understand the consequences of that thinking as related to self-views, social development, and interactions with parents, teachers, peers, and others who have a significant impact on the socialization process (Nimfa, 2014).

Darling (1999) argues that there are four parenting styles, including indulgent, authoritative, authoritarian, and uninvolved. This categorization is in accordance with their lowness or highness on parental responsiveness and demanding behaviour.

The term “demandingness” refers to how parents integrate into the community and family through their maturity expectations, disciplinary efforts, supervision, and willingness to confront a disruptive child, while “responsiveness” is defined as the ratio of fostering self-assertion and individuality by parents being attuned, accepting, and supportive of the demands and needs of children (Baumrind, 1966). Parents with higher levels of discipline, patterns of confrontation, and monitoring are considered demanding, whereas parents with a lower level of confrontation, inconsistent discipline, and monitoring are characterized as not demanding (Samiullah, 2016). This can be measured through the level of communication, reciprocity, and warmth displayed by parents while dealing with adolescents. In other words, parents emphasizing higher levels of reciprocal behaviour, warmth, and communication are considered to be highly responsive, whereas low levels of delineated factors represent low responsiveness.

The table below can be used to describe the four parenting styles according to the degree of demandingness and responsiveness as seen in Samiullah's 2016 study.

Table1: Types of Parenting Styles

DEGREE	LOW DEMANDINGNESS	HIGH DEMANDINGNESS
LOW RESPONSIVENESS	Neglecting parenting styles	Authoritarian parenting styles
HIGH RESPOSIVENESS	Permissive parenting styles	Authoritative parenting styles

Source: (Simons, Simons, & Wallace, 2004; Maccoby & Martin, 1983)

Authoritative parenting style

This style of parenting is more associated with positive adolescent outcomes. Piko & Balazs (2012) point out that the level of demandingness is higher, and parents who exhibit an authoritative parenting style usually welcome effective communication as well as an effective parent-child relationship.

The authoritative parenting style plays an influential role in the development of healthy adolescents psychologically and socially (Nijhof & Engels, 2007). This is particularly because the authoritative parenting style helps children develop a higher level of self-reliance, self-esteem, and the ability to employ effective coping strategies while developing a positive self-image.

Authoritarian parenting style

Children raised by authoritarian parents are expected to follow very strict rules defined by their parents or be punished if they fail to comply with those rules. In case the children fail to comply with such rules, they are punished. Cherry (2015) points out that authoritarian parents usually fail to come up with reasoning behind such rules. Authoritarian parents are highly demanding and exhibit low responsiveness (Hoskins, 2014).

Moreover, such parents discourage open communication, exert strict control over the child's behaviour, forceful child's behaviour, and demonstrate a low level of engagement and trust toward their children (Samiullah, 2016).

According to Nijhof and Engels (2007), the authoritarian parenting style is related to a lower level of ability and self-confidence in employing coping mechanisms among adolescents; hence, restricts a child

from exploring his/her capabilities and social interactions, eventually resulting in the child's dependence on parental guidance and direction.

Permissive and neglectful parenting styles

This type of parenting is said to have a higher level of responsiveness with a low level of demandingness. A permissive parent is more likely to define and determine rules associated with the family while encouraging the adolescents to consider them as options (Johnson & Kelley, 2011).

Permissive parents do not impose rules on their children; their children can do what they want when they want. Permissive parents can either be supportive (indulgent) or not care about their children (neglectful). This style of parenting can also be harmful to a developing child (Misty, 2002) while neglectful parents are those who show a very low level of involvement as well as strictness with their child (Kremers, Brug, de Vries, & Engels, 2003). Poduthase (2012) points out that adolescents can be led toward delinquent behaviour when they are exposed to a lack of intimacy, a lack of guidance, a lack of parental attachment, anger, and blaming.

2.1.2 ANTISOCIAL BEHAVIOUR

Antisocial behaviour, personality disorder, or conduct disorder, a term synonymous with delinquency was defined by Wachikwu and Ibegbunam (2012) as crimes committed by young people below the age of eighteen years, usually characterized by violations of existing social norms and values; it is also defined by Hanrahan (2006) as a disruptive act characterized by covert or overt hostility and intentional aggression towards others. It refers to an overall lack of adherence to the social norms and standards that allow members of a society coexist peacefully, and this varies worldwide and differs due to the social construct of the society.

People with antisocial personalities are known to have a low tolerance for frustration. They act on impulse, lose their temper quickly, lie easily and skillfully, are often bullies, fight, cheat, steal, and are truant from school. They blame others for their misdeeds, feel picked on by their parents and teachers, and never seem to learn from their mistakes (Lahey, 2003).

Antisocial behaviour can be classified into two different categories: covert and overt behaviours (Willoughby, Kupersmidt, & Bryant, 2001; Burt & Donnellan, 2009). The overt antisocial behaviour is confrontational behaviour that is not concealed, e.g. fighting, robbery, murder, and rape while covert antisocial behaviour is hidden and non-confrontational, e.g., lying, gossip, and disobedience (Johnson, 2012).

Types of Antisocial Behaviour

Antisocial behaviour can be grouped into three sub-types according to Burt and Donnellan, 2009 who used the sub-types of Antisocial Behaviour Questionnaire (STAB) to classify these behaviours.

1. Physical aggression includes fighting, physical bullying, getting angry, and having anger issues. and threatening others.
2. Social aggression is defined as behaviour that is harmful to those who are in social relationships. This type of behaviour can include gossiping, spreading rumour, purposefully trying to destroy other people reputation, deceit, body shaming, and envy.
3. Rule-breaking is any deliberate action violating the conduct or norm of a social group, which includes theft, administering illicit drugs, vandalism, littering, etc.

Researchers have not only investigated the types of antisocial behaviour; they have also researched the factors that possibly contribute to its formation. Some of the factors responsible for adolescents' antisocial behaviour include:

1. Nature of the home environment

The home and childhood experience have a lasting effect on the life of an individual. This can also give birth the kind of behaviour an individual portrays. Some children are nurtured in aversive, punitive, or violent environments, while others are nurtured in blissful environments with love, care, compassion, and understanding. Children raised in aversive and punitive environments are usually verbally abused, spanked, and sometimes injuries are inflicted on them for any perceived misconduct (real or imagined) by their primary caretakers; this can affect them physically and psychologically. In such homes, all the children can see is hatred, quarrels, bitterness, hostility, violence, competition, and pain. They accept misdemeanour as a way of life and may have no qualms about meting out this same treatment to the weaker ones (Nwanneka et al., 2015).

2. Socio-economic status of parents

The socio-economic status of parents cannot be overemphasized when dealing with behavioural pattern of an adolescent. Due to differences in socio-economic status, some adolescents are nurtured in a state of abject poverty, while others are nurtured in a state of affluence, and so their privileges differ. For those who are nurtured in a state of affluence, there is a high tendency not to be exposed to things that can endanger their lives in their quests for some basic needs, unlike those brought up in abject poverty (Nwanneka et al., 2015).

3. Age factor on adolescents

During late childhood through early adolescence, most children engage in physical aggression frequently, do not engage in physical aggression at all. Despite this, some children continue to engage in moderate or high levels of aggression through late childhood and into adolescence (Brame et al.,

2001; Dodge et al., 2006; Huesmann et al., 2009). Even for those children who do continue to engage in physical aggression during middle and late adolescence, the majority follow desisting trajectories. (Brame et al., 2001; Underwood et al., 2009).

4. Peer group influence

Peer group is a set of people who can be of the same age, status, or interest. Peer group association appears to exert influence on the behaviour of adolescents. An adolescent who belongs to a peer group whose members engage in antisocial activities such as underage smoking, alcoholism, pilfering, cultism, rape, prostitution and violence is most likely to imbibe these attitudes. Developmental theories, according to Monahan, Steinberg & Cauffman (2009), suggest that affiliation with deviant peers and susceptibility to peer influence are important contributors to adolescent delinquency (Monahan et al., 2009).

The effects of Antisocial Behaviour includes:

On the individual and family

Those who engage in antisocial behaviour considerably reduce their educational and employment opportunities; those who suffer from them must endure their physical, emotional, or economic challenges. In the social sphere, these problems consume a large amount of resources related to mental health, education, and juvenile justice (Sawyer et al., 2015). There is a high rate of transition from antisocial behaviour in adolescents to adult criminal activities (Hanrahan, 2006). It is opined that successful adults who once exhibited antisocial behaviour have a high tendency to be involved in white collar crimes (Nwanneka et al., 2015).

Economy

A country with high antisocial behaviour among its adolescents, youths, and adults risks having a poor or weak economy, as investors will be wary of putting money into doing business in such a country.

Unattractive destination for tourists

Nigeria is a country blessed with good vegetation and alluring tourist centers; however, this site has failed to attract tourists, especially foreigners, for fear of the menace of criminals (Nwanneka et al., 2015).

Unemployment

One of the effects of antisocial behaviour is a high unemployment rate caused by fraud and corruption. Perpetuated by children who stole, grew up stealing, and continue to steal in their respective positions. These individuals run around companies and misappropriate money meant to start up new businesses or to expand existing ones, and by doing so, they deny Nigerians employment opportunities. Some private companies have folded over the years due to an unhealthy business climate occasioned by the corrupt practices of those who exhibited antisocial behaviour in their adolescent years.

Infrastructural decay

When money allocated for the provision of basic infrastructure like the health sector, agriculture, the environment, and education is mismanaged through inflation of contract figures, bribery, and kickbacks, infrastructural decay is imminent.

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 ERIC ERICKSON THEORY OF IDENTITY DEVELOPMENT

The fifth stage of psychosocial development propounded by Eric Erickson, adolescents who, at this stage, struggle to discover his/her own identity while negotiating social interaction, "fitting in," and developing a sense of morality regarding right and wrong.

Eric Erickson believed that the primary psychological tasks of adolescence were establishing an identity. They begin to struggle with questions like "Who am I?" they include questions regarding their appearance, race, relationships, education, sexuality, political or religious beliefs of their parents. In 1980, Marcia expanded Erickson's work and identified four identity statuses based on whether a person has faced a crisis and made a commitment, which include: Identity (Diffusion, Moratorium, Foreclosure, Achievement).

Identity Diffusion: It is the least mature status and is common among children. It is characterized by those who have never explored their options nor made a commitment to an identity. Those who persist with this identity tend to have little sense of purpose in life.

Identity Moratorium: It is a status that describes those who explore different identities but are yet to make a commitment. It also refers to those who are in crisis about occupational or ideological decisions.

Identity Foreclosures: They have made a commitment, but their choices were influenced by others.

Identity Achievers: Having explored different identities, made a commitment to one. They experienced a period of decision-making and are now committed to an occupation and a set of ideological values, which are all self-chosen. They accept both their strengths and weaknesses, and they are considered adaptive and well-adjusted. Marcia agreed with Erickson that identity changes over time. As new roles and experiences are encountered, identity may change. The identity crisis is continually present and subject to new resolutions.

Table 2: Marcia's Four Identity Statuses

Commitment to an identity.	Exploration		
		Absent	Present
	Absent	Identity Diffusion	Identity Moratorium
	Present	Identity Foreclosure	Identity Achievement

The way an individual "see one self" can influence the adoption and expression of these roles and receptivity to antisocial opportunities, all of which, in turn, can shape and form an individual's perception of antisocial behaviour over time (Johnson, 2012)

2.3 EMPIRICAL FRAME WORK

It is generally believed that parenting style plays an influential role in developing delinquent behaviour among adolescents, which eventually results in negative outcomes (Kerr, Stattin & Ozdemir, 2012). The risk of an adolescent developing delinquent behaviour is often influenced by parenting style (Tompsett & Toro, 2010).

Based literature reviewed by Samiullah (2016), the researcher agreed that authoritarian parenting style oftentimes breeds children with antisocial behaviour due to the children reacting to a world they do not understand properly based on their parenting environment. It is related to the lower level of ability and self-confidence to employ coping mechanisms among adolescents.

Authoritative parenting styles enhance effective communication, which in turn builds effective relationship between child and parents. Demands made by parents are very much limited, and they also provide guidance to their children on issues oriented toward rational matters (Larzelere, Morris & Harrist, 2013).

Yang et al., 2014; Bernardo, 2014 proves that neglectful parents give children the liberty to actively participate in any action with less concern for consequences.

Parental practices characterized by love, affection, good parent- child communication and support are associated with low levels of antisocial behaviour in children, while a lack of affection, communication, and support is positively associated with antisocial behaviour in children, including drug use, criminal behaviour, active involvement in bullying, and disrespectful treatment of their parents, supported by (García & Gracia, 2009; Calvete et al., 2014; Hovee et al., 2011; Ginsburg et al., 2009; Kokkinos, 2013; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2015).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the study design, population of study, sampling technique, study area, research instrument, validation of the instrument, procedure for the administration of the instrument and method of data analysis.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research adopted a descriptive research design. A survey will be used as a technique for data collection from a sample of the population in order to determine the current status of that population with respect to the variable. The objective of this study is to explore the link between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour; determining the perception of adolescents towards antisocial behaviour in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government, Lagos State.

3.2 POPULATION OF STUDY

The targeted population of the study consisted of students and parents in four selected secondary schools (three public secondary schools and one private secondary school) in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government, Lagos State, Nigeria.

3.3 SAMPLE SIZE

A total number of 252 students were selected from the four schools.

3.4 SAMPLE TECHNIQUES

This study adopted a simple random sampling technique in the selection of senior secondary school students in the area. This will ensure that every student has a known and equal chance of being selected in the sample.

3.5 BRIEF HISTORY OF THE AREA OF STUDY

Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government Area of Lagos is a densely populated area in the northwestern part of Lagos State, Nigeria. It has a population of approximately 427,878 (NBS, 2006 Census) and was created by Gen. Sani Abacha on October 1, 1996. It was carved out of Agege Local Government and shares a boundary with Ogun State, Agege, Ikeja on the east, and Abule Egba on the west, giving it both the metropolitan intensity of Lagos State and the quiet of Ogun State. Major settlements within the Iako-Ijaiye include Ogba, Ifako, Obawole, Fagba, Iju-Ogundimu, Agege Pen Cinema, and Ojokoro, it is a blend of residential and vibrant commercial areas with its local economy driven by trade, informal commerce, artisanship, and small-scale manufacturing.

3.6 RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

A well-structured questionnaire was designed by the researcher to elicit responses from the respondents. The questionnaire is divided into four sections and was distributed for adolescents to

fill.

SECTION A-Assess the socioeconomic characteristics of respondents.

SECTION B-Examine relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour.

SECTION C-Examine the kinds of antisocial attitudes common in the area.

SECTION D-Assess perception of adolescents towards antisocial behaviour.

3.7 VALIDATION OF RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The validity content of the research instruments was assured by submitting a drafted questionnaire to senior researchers in the study of teenagers and antisocial behaviour for proper assessment and correction before administering.

3.8 RELIABILITY OF RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Thirty- five (35) copies of the structured questionnaire were administered for pilot at Oke-Odo Senior High School, Agbado/Oke-Odo Local Government, Lagos state. The reliability of the instrument was adopted at a Cronbach alpha of 0.843.

3.10 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The study employed using frequency count, percentages, Mean, Pie, Bar Chart and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

This chapter present result of the research carried out on exploring the link between parenting style and adolescent antisocial behaviour in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government, Lagos State. Five research questions and one hypothesis were formulated and tested. The data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC). The summary of the data analysis is discussed below.

4.1 Analysis of Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

RQ1: What are the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents?

Table 4.1.1 presents the frequency distribution according to the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The results revealed that 94 representing 37.3% of the respondents, were male, while 158 of them, or 62.7% were female. It implies that the majority of the respondents were female. The result showed that respondents those aged 19 - 21 years were 9(3.6%), age 10 - 12 years were 43(17.1%), age 13 - 15 years were 99(39.3%), respondents within the age range of 16-18 years had the highest population with 101(40.0%). The table showed that 189 representing 75% of the respondents, were from public schools, and 63 of them, or 25% were from private schools, respectively; this implies that the majority of the respondents were from public schools. Furthermore, the table showed that 119 representing 47.2% of the respondents, were Muslim, 105(41.7%) of the respondents were Christians, 17(6.7%) were African Traditional Religion practitioners, and 11(4.4%) declined to declare their religion. It implies that the majority of the respondents were Muslim. The table showed SS1 class presented 63(25%) of the respondents, SS2 had 98(38.9%) of respondents, which signifies the largest population of respondents and SS3 had 91(36.1%) of the total respondent.

Table 4.1.1: Socio-Demographic Characteristic of the Respondents (n =252)

Socio-Demographic		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	94	37.0
	Female	158	62.7
Age group	10 - 12 years	43	17.1
	13 - 15 years	99	39.3
	16 - 18 years	101	40.0
	19 - 21 years	9	3.6
Type of School	Public School	189	75
	Private Schhol	63	25
Religion	Islam	119	47.2
	Christianity	105	41.7
	ATR	17	5.7
	Others	11	4.4
Current Class	SS1	63	25
	SS2	98	38.9
	SS3	91	36.1

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4.2 Socio-Demographic Characteristic of the Parents

Table and Figure 4.2.1 the frequency distribution according to fathers' occupations of the respondents. The results showed that 73(29.0%) had fathers who were civil servants and businessmen respectively, traders 37(13.9%), teachers 13(5.2%), engineers 23(9.1%), 3(1.2%) were farmers, and 9(3.6%) had fathers who were artisans. Respondents whose fathers were lecturers numbered 6(2.4%), accountants 8(3.2%), doctors 1(0.4) and Force man 4(1.6%), 2 respondents respectively had fathers who were either clergymen or musicians. This showed that civil service and Business had the largest population of fathers' occupations.

Table 4.2.1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Father' s Occupation (n =252)

Father Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Civil servant	73	29.0
Business	73	29.0
Trading	37	14.6
Teacher	13	5.1
Engineer	23	9.1
Farming	3	1.1
Artisan	9	3.5
Lecturer	6	2.3
Accountant	8	3.1
Doctor	1	0.3
Clergy Man	2	0.8
Force man	4	1.5
Musician	2	0.8

Figure 4.2.1: Pie Chart Distribution of Respondents by Father' s Occupation

Table and Figure 4.2.2 reveal the frequency distribution according to the occupation of the respondents. The result showed that civil servants were 40(15.9%) and businesswomen were 55(21.8%) while traders were 104(41.3%), and teachers were 23(9.1%), medical officers were 8(3.2%), farmers and school matrons were 2(0.8%), artisans were 8(3.2%) those occupied with a lecturing job were 4(1.6%), and nurses were 1(0.4%) while housewives were 5(2.0%) of the total respondents. This showed that traders had the highest frequency.

Table 4.2.2: Frequency distribution of respondents by mother's occupation (n =252)

Mother Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Civil servant	40	15.9
Business	55	21.8
Trading	104	41.3
Teacher	23	9.1
Doctor	8	3.2
Farming	2	0.8
Artisan	8	3.2
School matron	2	0.8
Lecturer	4	1.6
Nurse	1	0.4
Housewife	5	2.0
Total	252	100.0

Table and Figure 4.2.3 revealed the frequency distribution according to the educational level of the respondents' fathers. The result showed that respondents with no formal education were 49 (19.4%) while

those with OND were 43(17.0%), NCE holders were 27(10.7%) while respondents' father with HND certificate were 69(27.5%), B.Sc. were 44(17.46%), MSc holders were 14(5.5%) while PhD were 6(2.4%) of the total respondents. This showed that respondents with HND had the highest frequency.

Table 4.2.3:Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Father’s Education (n =252)

Father Education	Frequency	Percentage
No formal Education	49	19.4
OND	43	17.0
NCE	27	10.7
HND	69	27.5
B.Sc.	44	17.5
M.Sc.	14	5.5
PhD.	6	2.38

Table and Figure 4.2.4 revealed the frequency distribution according to Mother Education of the respondents. The result showed that respondents with no formal education were 61(24.2%) while those with OND were 75(29.8%), NCE holders were 33(13.1%) while those with HND certificate were 29(11.5%), B.Sc. were 28(11.1%), MSc. holder were 17(6.respondents7%) while PhD were 9(3.5%) of the total respondent. This showed that respondents with mothers who had an OND had the highest frequency.

Table 4.2.4: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Mother's Education (n =252)

Mother's Education	Frequency	Percentage
No formal Education	61	24.3
OND	75	29.8
NCE	33	13.1
HND	29	11.5
B.Sc.	28	11.1
M.Sc.	17	6.7
Ph.D.	9	3.57

Table and Figure 4.2.5 revealed that 207 representing 82.1% of the respondents, were from monogamous homes, while 45 of them, which made up 17.9% were from polygamous families. Therefore, the above result implies that the majority of the respondents were from monogamous homes.

Table 4.2.5: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Type of Family (n =252)

Type of Family	Frequency	Percentage
Monogamous	202	80.1
Polygamous	50	19.9

Table and Figure 4.2.6 revealed that 146 representing 57.9% of the respondents, were married, and 48 of them, or 19.0% were divorced. Single parents were 28 (11.2%) and widowed individuals were 30 (11.9%) of the total respondents. The result below implies that majority of respondents were married.

Table 4.2.6: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Type of Family (n =252)

Type of Family	Frequency	Percentage
Married	146	57.9
Divorced	48	19.0
Single Parent	28	11.2
Widowed	30	11.9

Table and Figure 4.2.7 show that 199 representing 79.0% of the respondents, said their parents lived together, and 53 (21.0%) of them disagreed, saying their parents no longer live together.

Table 4.2.7: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by whether their parents live together (n =252)

Parent living together	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	199	79.0
No	53	21.0

Table and Figure 4.2.8 reveal that 147 representing 58.3% of the respondents, live with their mother; 67 of them, or 26.6% live with an aunt; 2.0% live with their mother's friends; and 22 (8.7%) live with their stepmother, while 11(4.4%) live with their brothers. This shows that most of the respondents live with their mothers.

Table 4.2.8: Frequency distribution of respondents by whom they live with (n =252)

Living with	Frequency	Percentage
Mother	147	58.3
Aunty	67	26.6
Mummy’s friend	5	2.0
Step Mother	22	8.7
Brother	11	4.4

Table and Figure 4.2.9 reveal that 117 representing 46.4% of the total, indicated that parents were responsible for school fees, and 38 of them, or 15.1% said sisters, while brother was 21 (8.3%) of the total respondents. Mother paying school fees had a frequency size of 36 (14.3%), school fees paying fathers were 40 (15.9%). Parents were responsible for paying the school fees for most respondents.

Table 4.2.9: Frequency distribution of respondents by who pays their school fees (n =252)

Responsible for school fees	Frequency	Percentage
Parent	117	46.4
Sister	38	15.1
Brother	21	8.3
Mother	36	14.3
Father	40	15.9

Table and Figure 4.2.10 show that 68 respondents, which represent 27.0% of the total population, indicated that they lived in duplexes, and 57(22.6%) of them lived in bungalows and storey buildings, respectively. Living in room- to - room or room & palour residence was selected by 35(13.9%) of respondents..

Table 4.2.10: Frequency distribution of respondents by the type of residence they live in (n =252)

Type of residence	Frequency	Percentage
Duplex	68	27.0
Bungalow	57	22.6
Storey building	57	22.6
Room - Room	35	13.9
Room & Palour	35	13.9

4.3 Research Questions

RQ2: What is the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour in adolescents?

The responses on the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour in adolescents were rated in Table 4.3.1. as shown below. Respondents who said their parents always tell or shout when they misbehave were 90.9% while 9.1% of them said their parents don't tell or shout when they misbehave; the mean is 2.58, followed by 88.9% of respondents who said their parents always praise them when they behave well, and 11.1% said their parents never praise them when they are well-behaved, supported by a mean of 2.47. Being encouraged by their parents to talk about their troubles ranked third with a mean of 2.42, as 85.7% of respondents said their parents encourage them to do this while 14.3% said their parents never, also, 85.3% of respondents said their parents always give comfort and understanding when they are upset and 14.7% indicated never and supported the claim with a mean of 2.37.

Furthermore, 60.7% of the study population said their parents always punish them to by taking privileges away from them by little or no explanation, while 39.3% said their parents don't take away privileges. The mean is 1.88, respondents (57.6%) said their parents always withhold criticism and/or scolding, even when they act contrary to their wishes, while 42.4% indicated that their parents don't hold back criticism and/or scolding, supported by a mean of 1.83. Allowing them to annoy/vex someone else was ranked with a mean of 1.59 with 81.3% of respondents saying their parents never allow them to do such, and 28.7% agreed that their parents allow them to do such. Also, 83.0% of respondents said their parents always talk it over and reason with them when they misbehave, while 17.0% said it never happens, supported by a mean of 2.37. Parents always helping children understand the impact of their behaviour by encouraging them to talk about the consequences of their actions had a mean ranking of 2.33 as 82.1% of respondents say their parents do this, while 17.9% disagree.

Criticism when behaviour does not meet parents' expectations had a mean value of 2.24 with 81.0% of respondents disagreeing, while 19.0% agreed. Majority of the respondents (73.4%) agreed that their parents always explode in anger towards them, while 26.6% disagreed, with a mean value of 1.98.

"I conform because I have to," as stated by my parents, ranked with a mean of 1.93, as 65.5% of respondents do this compared to 34.1% of their colleagues who do not conform. In addition, 65.9% agreed that their parents only state punishment without, carrying it out and 34.1%

disagreed. Finally, 48.8% of respondents stated that their mothers always appear unsure on how to deal with their misbehaviour while 51.2% said their mothers were never unsure of what to do, mean is 1.69.

The results imply that the majority of the respondents believe there is a negative relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour in adolescents, as represented by a weighted mean value of 2.13. It was affirmed based on this research that the majority of respondents claim their parents have a positive attitude towards them.

S/N	Identification of parenting styles	Types of parenting	Always (%)	Once in a while (%)	Never (%)	x	Rank
1	My parents encourages me to talk about my troubles	Authoritative	143 (56.7)	73 (29.0)	36 (14.3)	2.42	2
2	My parents praises me when behave well	Authoritative	173 (68.7)	51 (20.2)	28 (11.1)	2.47	1
3	My parents withhold scolding/criticizing even when I act contrary to their wishes	Permissive	77 (30.6)	68x (27.0)	107 (42.5)	1.83	13
4	They punish me by taking privileges away from me with little if any explanation	Authoritarian	57 (22.6)	96 (38.1)	99 (39.3)	1.88	12
5	My parents give me comfort and understanding when I am upset	Authoritative	131 (52.0)	84 (33.3)	37 (14.7)	2.39	4
6	My parents yells or shout when I misbehave	Authoritarian	141 (56.0)	88 (34.9)	23 (9.1)	2.58	3
7	My parents are Easy going and relaxed with me	Permissive	142 (56.3)	66 (26.2)	44 (17.5)	2.37	5
8	My parents allow mne to annoy someone else	Permissive	47 (18.7)	54 (21.4)	151 (59.9)	1.59	15
9	They state punishments to me and does notactually do them	Permissive	61 (24.2)	105 (41.7)	86 (34.1)	1.90	11

10	My parents help me to understand the impact of my behaviour by encouraging me to talk about the consequences of my action	Authoritative	129 (51.2)	78 (31.0)	45 (17.9)	3 23	7
11	My Parents explode in anger towards me	Authoritarian	61 (24.2)	124 (49.2)	67 (26.6)	1.98	9
12	They talk it over and reason with me when I misbehave	Authoritative	135 (53.6)	74 (29.4)	43 (17.0)	2.37	6
13	They criticize or scold when my behaviour does not meet their expectation	Authoritarian	108 (42.9)	96 (38.1)	48 (19.0)	2.24	8
14	When I ask why I have to conform,they state because I said so,or I am your parents and I wants you to	Authoritarian	69 (27.4)	96 (38.1)	87 (34.5)	1.93	10
15	My mother appear unsure on how to solve my misbehaviour	Permissive	51 (20.2)	72 (28.6)	129 (51.2)	1.69	14

WEIGHED MEAN VALUE

2.13

RQ3: What are the kinds of antisocial behaviour common in the area?

The responses regarding the kinds of antisocial behaviour common in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government are ranked and shown in Table 4.3.2 below, 97.6% of respondents said fistfighting was a misbehaviour they had engaged in, while 2.4% said they had never had a fistfight. The mean is 2.74, and purposely damaging someone else's property was another serious antisocial behaviour with a mean value of 2.72, 96.4% of respondents have done this, while 3.6% said they have never. Also, 96.0% of respondents said the use of non-lethal weapons to fight was common for them, while 4.0% disagreed to this and it has a mean value of 2.69, engaging in group fights had 96.0% disagreeing and 4.0% agreeing, mean of 2.62. Taking money without permission or without the intent of saying anything, mean of 2.60 had 94.9% of respondents actively participating, and 5.2% said they don't take money without permission.

In addition, 94.0% of respondents have hurt someone who hasn't done anything wrong just because they can, while 6.0% said they have never done so, mean of 2.47, finally, forcing someone to do something they don't want to do or hitting them to get them to do something, mean of 2.46, had 85.3% of respondents agreeing to have done so and 14.7% saying never.

The result implies that the majority of the respondents believe these kinds of antisocial behaviour are common in the study area, as represented with a standard mean value of 2.61 and that society's belief kinds of antisocial behaviour common in the study area was discouraging, represented with a standard mean of 2.46.

Table 4.3.2: Common antisocial behaviour in the study area (n =252)

S/N	Items	Never (%)	Once or Twice (%)	Several times (%)	\bar{x}	Rank
1	Threatened to hit someone or force them to do something they did not want to do?	37 (14.7)	63	152 (60.3)	2.46	7
2	Taken part in fights between groups of youths (gang)	10 (4.0)	51 (20.2)	191 (75.8)	2.62	4
3	Purposely broke or destroyed something that didn't belong to you?	9 (3.6)	59 (23.4)	184 (73.0)	2.72	2
4	Used a weapon in a fight with someone else?	10 (4.0)	46 (18.3)	196 (77.8)	2.69	3
5	Taken money from the house without permission, or without the intent of saying anything?	13 (5.2)	71 (28.2)	168 (66.7)	2.60	5
6	Hit someone who hasn't done anything wrong?	15 (6.0)	72 (28.6)	165 (65.5)	2.47	6
7	Had a fistfight with anyone?	6 (2.4)	121 (48.0)	125 (49.6)	2.74	1
Weighed mean value					2.61	

RQ4: What is the perception of respondents on antisocial behaviour?

The responses on the perception of respondents on antisocial behaviour were rated as shown in Table 4.3.4 below. Paying close attention, a mean of 1.67, has 67.5% of respondents agreeing to do that when told, while 32.5% do not pay close attention. Being on their best behaviour so as not to embarrass parents had mean value of 1.57, 57.1% of respondents agreed to this, and 42.9% disagreed. Also, 53.6% of respondents say the more parents try to stop them, from doing something the more determined to do such, this has a 46.6% of respondents disagreeing that it is not so with them and it has a mean value of 1.54

Furthermore, 52.4% of respondents said that when told to stop an act or action, it is easy for them to stop; 47.6% said it is not easy to stop. Mean value is 1.52.

Attachment to friends and engaging in whatever they do (=1.34) has 33.7% of respondents agreeing with it, while 66.3% disagree. With a mean value of 1.30, 29.8% of respondents said they have drunk alcohol with friends since their parents also do it, while 70.2% have never drunk alcohol. I am old enough to decide what is good or bad for myself, with a mean value of 1.29 with 28.6 saying it's so true and 71.4 % disagree. Finally, 77.8% go to school because they need to, and 27.4% go to school when they feel like, mean value is 1.22

The result implies that the majority of respondents have a negative perception of antisocial behaviour, represented with a standard mean value of 1.43 and that society has a negative perception of respondents regarding antisocial behaviour discouraging it, represented with a standard mean of 1.30.

Table 4.3.3: Perception of respondents on antisocial behaviour

S/N	Items	No (%)	Yes (%)	\bar{x}	Rank
1	No one can tell me what is good or bad, I am old enough to decide what I want	180 (71.4)	72 (28.6)	1.29	7
2	I go to school when I feel the need to do so	196 (77.8)	56 (22.2)	1.22	8
3	I always like to behave in a way that will not embarrass my parents. They are too good to be offended	108 (42.9)	144 (57.1)	1.57	2
4	I always attach myself to my friends and engage in whatever they do so I can belong	167 (66.3)	85 (33.7)	1.34	5
5	My parents drink alcohol in my presence so I drink when I am with my friends too	177 (70.2)	75 (29.8)	1.30	6
6	When someone tells me to stop doing something, it is easy for me to stop	120 (47.6)	132 (52.4)	1.52	4
7	The more I try to stop myself from doing something I shouldn't, the more likely I am to do it	117 (46.4)	135 (53.6)	1.54	3
8	I pay close attention when someone tells me how to do something	82 (32.5)	170 (67.5)	1.67	1
Weighed mean value				1.43	

4.4 Hypothesis

H01: There is no significant relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour among adolescents.

Table 4.4.1 below shows that there was a significant relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour ($r = .971^{**}$, $N = 252$, $p = 0.000 < .05$) among adolescents. Thus the hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there was a significant relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Parenting styles	31.97	4.601	252	.971**	.000	Sig.
Antisocial behaviour	22.26	2.544				

*Sig. at .05 level

4.5 DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

This chapter gives the whole summary of the research work. The results obtained from the study show the relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour among adolescents from four secondary schools in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government of Lagos State. The study revealed the following:

The research carried out descriptive statistics on randomly selected adolescents who were primarily ages 16-18 years (40.0%) and were female (62.7%). It was deduced that 29.0% of their fathers were either civil servants or businessmen, while 41.3% of their mothers were traders. The common type of marriage practiced is monogamy (80.1%) and 76.6% of the respondents lived with their parents, who catered to their school fees.

The study revealed the types and attributes of parenting styles exhibited by their parents. It was observed that a large percentage of respondents' parents practiced an authoritative parenting style, as 68.7% of respondents said their parents praised them when they behaved well, and 56.7% of respondents had parents who encouraged them to talk about their troubles.

It is also revealed that a significant percentage of the parents practiced an authoritarian parenting style, as 49.2% of respondents said their parents exploded in anger towards them occasionally, and 42.9% said their parents always scolded or criticized them when their behaviour did not meet expectations.

The study also revealed that antisocial behaviour is prominent among respondents, as 73% of them said they had purposely broken or destroyed something that did not belong to them several times, 49.6% had fistfights with people on many occasions, 77.8% had used non-lethal weapons (stick, stone) while fighting on several occasions, and 24.2% had taken part in gang-related fights. This, however, shows that there is a high rate of antisocial behaviour common in the study area.

The hypothesis tested shows that there is a significant relationship between parenting styles and antisocial behaviour among adolescents in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government of Lagos State. This supports the work of Johnson (2012) who stated that negative parenting and antisocial behaviour would be related and was supported by the results of this study. It also supports the work of Thomas et al., 2007 which states that parenting styles are associated with antisocial behaviour (the more extreme the parenting environment, the worse the child outcome). This proves that a

"one parenting style fits all" approach is not optimal; there might be a need to combine two or more parenting styles.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.1 Summary

The objective of this study was to link parenting styles to antisocial behaviour among adolescents in Ifako-Ijaiye Local Government of Lagos State.

Results of the study showed:

- ❖ Antisocial behaviour was common among middle adolescents in the study area.
- ❖ Parenting style was linked as one of the factors responsible for the antisocial behaviour of adolescents in the study area.

5.2 Conclusion

Antisocial behaviour is a part of everyday life, and it affects millions of people worldwide; therefore, it is important to carefully examine it, understand what it is, the factors responsible for it, and how to curb it at its onset. Positive parenting would lead to a decrease in antisocial behaviour, creating a better society and world.

5.3 Recommendation

- ❖ Family focused programs should be organised for parents to help develop and maintain effective monitoring and discipline strategies.
- ❖ Effective education on the implications and benefits of prosocial behaviour for adolescents should be organised regularly.
- ❖ Government and policymakers should work to curb other factors, aside from parenting styles, responsible for antisocial behaviour among adolescents.

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